

Communication and Outreach Strategy

Open Urban Sustainability Hubs (OPUSH) project |
ERA-Net Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC)

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Summary

Effective and strategic communication is an essential tool that will help OPUSH achieve its results and involve all relevant stakeholders. Centralised communication channels, such as the project website and social media accounts have been established to communicate project objectives and results to a wider audience. However, due to the localised nature of the project and its activities, the consortium has chosen to pursue more decentralised communication channels as primary outreach tools to better reach the identified target audiences.

This communication and outreach strategy identifies communication goals and guiding principles, target audiences and associated communication approaches for each audience, as well as communication channels and materials that will be used throughout project implementation. The flexible nature of the strategy and its continuous evaluation and adjustment are given special attention so as to ensure the effectiveness of project communication and outreach overtime.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Alt text	Alternative text
CSO	Civil society organisation
GLAM	Galleries, libraries, archives and museums
OPUSH	Open Urban Sustainability Hubs

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Introduction

1. About the project

OPUSH is a citizen science project for identifying and collaboratively finding practical and policy solutions to the most pressing issues within social and environmental justice and affordable housing in Barcelona, Tallinn, Delft and Vienna.

2. Goals

We aim to identify relevant issues, jointly develop an easily-accessible, inclusive and open platform, as well as tools and processes for collaboration between researchers, libraries, decision-makers and citizens. This will help bring scientists, local administrators and communities closer together, as well as empower and facilitate them working jointly to formulate strategies/policy recommendations and design a roadmap for sustainable urban transformation.

3. Participants and activities

OPUSH engages people from local universities, galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM), local administrators and people from local communities without restriction to their age, socio-economic status, gender and/or beliefs.

Having identified specific issues of concern for the local communities, all participants will select a tool for collaboration and create a knowledge hub that will serve as a safe space for discussion of issues and solutions as well as tapping into available knowledge on the issues in question.

The knowledge hubs will provide a safe space for dialogue, build trust and mediate conflict between all involved. While no prior experience is required to take part, participants will receive training on the process of joint problem-solving and decision-making. Webinars and other training activities on sustainable development, social and environmental justice, affordable housing will be organised for library and GLAM staff, higher education communities and citizens. Open online resources will be produced and made available for all participants.

4. Communication and outreach

Effective and strategically planned communication and outreach is the first step towards reach these goals. Objectives specified in this Communications and Outreach Activities Strategy Plan (herein after referred to as Communications and Outreach Strategy) set the working tone for the rest of project implementation and span until the project completion. OPUSH aims to build a community of diverse local stakeholders and hubs to support their work to foster sustainable urban transformation, which is why the communication and outreach strategy is centred around stakeholders. For this reason a more decentralised approach has been chosen to ensure effective project implementation.

This strategy document identifies:

- Communication goals and principles,
- Target groups and communication strategy per each group,
- Channels of communication, why they have been chosen and how they will be used,

- Communication materials to be created for branding purposes,
- Acknowledgement of EU funding, and
- Continuous monitoring and adjustment.

Communication goals and principles

1. Communication goals

This Communication and Outreach Strategy serves as a coordination tool for effective communication of project activities and results. As such, this is a living document that will be adjusted throughout project implementation. The following are specific goals that guide project communication:

- 1) Maximize visibility and transparency through providing information about the project, its goals, activities and results to all stakeholders.
- 2) Demonstrate impact through sharing project results with all relevant stakeholders.
- 3) Facilitate engagement between all project stakeholders.

2. Guiding principles

Project communication aims to facilitate collaboration between all project stakeholders. Based on this understanding, the communications and outreach strategy takes a stakeholder/target group-centric approach to ensure such collaboration is fostered with specific needs of each stakeholder group in mind. A necessary element of ensuring effectiveness of such targeted approach is early and effective conversation with all stakeholders.

Given the local nature of the project and its focus on connecting citizens, libraries, researchers and local administration in the process, some of the communication materials will be translated into local languages to achieve maximum targeted reach. An evaluation of whether any of the key outputs or their parts would achieve better reach in local languages will guide the decision on what documents will be translated. All project outputs will be uploaded into the project repository in open access based on the FAIR data principles, and delivered to stakeholders in a targeted approach.

News from the project activities and outputs will be regularly published on the project website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram). When such news are specific to local audiences, the information on the website and social media will be posted in local languages and often through local stakeholders' accounts to better reach the intended audience.

All communication within and outside of the project will follow three principles:

a. Communication is transparent

The focus of this citizen social science project is to pilot a participatory process for urban transformation within the sustainability agenda. Transparency is a guiding principle of any such citizen science projects, as it allows participants to freely engage at any stage of project design and/or implementation. Transparent communication is key to achieving project and communication results and will guide all internal and external communication within OPUSH.

b. Communication is inclusive and accessible

OPUSH targets, among other stakeholders, citizens that represent a wide variety of socio-economic statuses, gender, etc. As such, all communication within the project aims to be inclusive and accessible to accommodate these various stakeholders. Information will be provided in local languages where possible. Special arrangements will be made to ensure accessibility of all communication materials and channels/events following the principle of ‘reasonable accommodation’¹. Alt text² will be utilised where relevant.

c. Communication is coordinated

OPUSH foresees a local approach to project implementation to ensure all local characteristics are taken into account for better targeted results. However, communication will be centrally coordinated to allow for the use of expertise across consortium partners to its fullest extent, and guide the adherence to jointly agreed upon principles in this document.

Target groups

Communication activities will follow a target group-centred approach. Given the localized nature of the project, local targeted communication will be prioritized over centralised project communication.

The following have been identified as main target groups for communication purposes and communication and outreach approaches to them:

Primary target groups

- **Local administration**

Local administration is one of the key target audiences of OPUSH. Local administration will serve as a project partner when the project reaches its piloting stage. As such, consortium partners will establish close cooperation with local administration at an early stage through meetings and participation in project workshops. Further communication activities will include meetings and discussions, workshops, clustering with relevant networks, engagement in project workshops and joint communication activities.

- **Actors involved in the urban planning systems**

Such actors will also serve as essential partners for local piloting, as they represent stakeholders involved in all levels of urban planning. Communication with this target group will be established with support of local administration and will take the form of meetings and participation in project workshops. Other communication activities will

¹ ‘Reasonable accommodation’, as referred to in Article 2 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, “means necessary and appropriate modification and adjustments not imposing a disproportionate or undue burden, where needed in a particular case, to ensure to persons with disabilities the enjoyment or exercise on an equal basis with others of all human rights and fundamental freedoms.” <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities/article-2-definitions.html>

² “Alt text” refers to “alternative text” conveys “the “why” of the image as it relates to the content of a document or webpage. It is read aloud to users by screen reader software, and it is indexed by search engines. It also displays on the page if the image fails to load.” <https://accessibility.huit.harvard.edu/describe-content-images>

include clustering with relevant networks, engagement in project workshops and joint communication activities.

- **Civil Society Organisations (CSOs)**

CSOs will play an important role in connecting the project with citizens, as well as representing their interests and supporting the development of solutions throughout the project. While personal contact will be established through meetings and workshops with CSOs, social media and project website will play an important role in reaching the CSOs and allowing them to assist in recruitment of citizens to participate in the project. As with other actors, local communication channels will be utilised where appropriate.

- **Citizens**

Citizens represent one of the stakeholder and target audience groups that is the most difficult to reach. As such, communication and outreach plan for reaching this group will remain flexible and rely on local channels of all involved stakeholders, local events, project workshops as well as project social media accounts and website.

- **Galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) institutions**

GLAM institutions represent an important local partner for the project that will be involved throughout the project implementation and, potentially, guarantee sustainability of project results as the hosts for the hubs envisaged by the project. For this target group, main communication activities include meetings and discussions, workshops, clustering with relevant networks, engagement in project workshops, as well as participation of consortium partners in events organized by third parties, joint communication activities.

Secondary target group:

- **Academics (CS and Urban Planning)**

The main communication activities for this target group include contribution to and participation in scientific conferences, forums, publications in scientific journals, social media, dissemination of project results through project website. Relevant academic events will be announced on the OPUSH website and the coLab space.

Communication channels

This section covers the communication channels that will be primarily used by the project. Such channels include:

- Project website
- Social media
- Blogposts
- Local administration and partners' own communication channels

Project website, social media and blogposts are coordinated by WP5 with direct input and cooperation from all consortium partners. Key updates within these channels will be research results, reports and other deliverables, events of any kind and meetings.

Besides this coordinated communication, partners are expected to use their local means of communication, be they institutional or those of local administration or CSOs.

1. Website

The following website has been created to serve as the central aggregate of all relevant public information about the project and other relevant citizen science news: <http://opush.net/index.php>

While the project is in its initial stages and has not generated much publicly-relevant content, the website is limited to displaying the general project information and partners involved. As the project progresses, more content will be added and strategies for stakeholder engagement, such as comment sections on the deliverables, will be activated.

Currently, the top menu of the website includes the following sections:

- Home
- About Team
- News
- Contact

Links to the project social media will be included on the homepage when the social media channels are established.

The 'home' section provides short information about the project, featured news, links to other inspirational citizen science projects, project goals and partners involved in the project.

Users can learn more about the project in the 'about' section and about project partners in the 'team' tab. 'News' section hosts relevant project and citizen science news in their original languages, and will be continuously updated to remain relevant. For questions, clarification or participation requests, the 'contact' tab contains a contact form that is linked to the project email account.

The website structure is simple and intuitive to ensure the ease of use and clean look and feel. The primary objectives of the website is to promote the project, disseminate its outputs and discuss them with relevant stakeholders.

2. Social media

Social media is one of the main communication channels for the OPUSH project. It allows the partners to connect to a wider target audience through the media channel of their choosing, as well as follow ongoing developments, including social issues that are important for the citizens. OPUSH will make use of the following media channels and professional networks: Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook. Through establishing a two-way communication channel with its stakeholders through the channels that are convenient for them the project will foster a stronger and better community.

3. Blogposts

Another tool for project engagement activities and outreach is a blog established on the OPUSH website. The blog will be used by all partners to describe their activities,

engage citizens in a conversation through the comment function, as well as update them on what is going on in their area and how to get involved. Blogposts will be posted either in English, or a local language or both, depending on the target audience for each entry.

4. Local administration and partners own communication channels

Due to the localised nature of the project, keeping communication local is essential. To ensure project messages reach the right target audience, communication channels of local administration, CSOs, GLAM institutions and wider urban planning structures will be utilised. Partners will use local languages for their messaging wherever necessary to eliminate any potential barriers for participation of the local stakeholders.

5. Events

To maximise the impact of the project results, events in a variety of formats (workshops, webinars, coordination meetings, etc.) will be organised throughout project duration. Project partners will also participate in third-party events related to citizen science, urban transformation and sustainability, where they will be able to present the project and its results to a wider audience. All documents (posters, presentations) produced for such events will be made openly available in the project repository, its website and further promoted through social media.

Communication materials

1. Project logo, colours, fonts and document templates

To build a project visual identity and better translate its goals for the target audiences, a logo that focuses on the citizen science and sustainability foci of the project has been created.

Another aspect of visual identity that will guide the development of all communication materials is fonts, their sizes and colours. These have been chosen in accordance with the principle of visual accessibility and cultural neutrality:

- **Font:** Arial
- **Preferred font size:** 12pt
- **Preferred font colors:** black, light green/blue.

The most common and widely available font that is accessible for people with visual impairment is **Arial**. It has therefore been chosen for project communication to ensure brand consistency and accessibility. Suggested font size for body text is **12 point**, and 9 point for footnotes.

Additionally, alt text should be used in all electronic communication to ensure all images are readable by screen readers and browsers that block images.

To ensure project visual identity is consistent, guiding principles for project communication are adhered to, and to simplify the process of communication materials creation, the following templates have been designed and made available in coLAB for consortium use:

- Reports
- PPT template

- Blogpost template
- Deliverable template
- Poster template for conferences (A1 and A2 sizes)
- Information flyer for citizens
- Public reports template

Responsibilities and acknowledgement of EU funding

WP5 'Capacity Building and Dissemination' is responsible for regular updates of the communication and outreach strategy in consultation with project partners. The WP5 has created templates and materials as part of the project visual identity that follows strategic project communication guidelines, which are available in the collaborative project platform coLAB. All project partners are expected to contribute to communication, dissemination and impact.

OPUSH partners are committed to acknowledging the EU funding in all dissemination and communication activities, as stated in the Grant Agreement. As such, all dissemination outputs must:

- display the EU emblem and
- include the following text: "This project has received funding from funding from ERA-NET joint call for research and innovation projects on Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC), co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101003758".

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency.

The EU emblem and all needed material is provided in the coLAB platform for the project.

Continuous monitoring and adjustment

WP5 will regularly evaluate all communication and outreach activities, including partner experience in organising local events and pilots. Based on such evaluation, adjustments to the strategy and its implementation will be performed.

A joint document with information about all activities organised by project partners will be created. The document will contain information about the types of activities, their dates and number of participants involved per stakeholder category. The document will be jointly updated by all consortium partners and stored in the project coLab space.

Data about the reach of all project activities on social media, website, project publications will also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of the chosen strategy and suggest changes where necessary.

